

University Questionnaire

This questionnaire was used in stage 3 of the following study, and is intended to explore EMI at the macro-level of the university, and filled in by people in high-level administrative positions:

Sahan, K., Mikolajewska, A., **Rose, H.**, Macaro, E. Searle, M., Aizawa, I., Zhou, S., and Veitch, A. (2021). *Global mapping of English as a medium of instruction in higher education: 2020 and beyond*. London: British Council.

Start of Block: Welcome message

Global Mapping of English Medium Instruction (EMI) in Higher Education: 2020 and beyond

Study Information Sheet

We would like to invite you to participate in a research project entitled 'Global Mapping of English Medium Instruction (EMI) in Higher Education: 2020 and beyond'. This project is led by the Department of Education, University of Oxford in collaboration with British Council, and aims to explore the expansion of English in higher education in universities around the world.

You will be asked to fill in a questionnaire about the use of English to teach degree subjects at your university. Note, we are not investigating the teaching of English language, but rather the use of English to teach subjects such as sciences, mathematics, medicine, and social sciences.

If you agree to participate, your input will form part of research into the use of English to teach in university settings. Participation is completely voluntary.

The findings from the research will be presented at an online event hosted by the Department of Education, University of Oxford, later this year. If you choose to participate, you or a representative from your university will be invited to attend the free online event. The research might also be published in academic journals and conference papers in the future, which may be publicly available. We would be happy to share with you any information that will be used in publications prior to their dissemination. The researcher will take steps ensure that any data

from you that appears in a publication will not be identifiable. Your university will not be identified in publications.

This project has been reviewed by, and received ethics clearance through, the University of Oxford Central University Research Ethics Committee. If you have any questions, please feel free to contact the lead investigator by e-mail: heath.rose@education.ox.ac.uk .

Yours Sincerely,
Dr. Heath Rose (The University of Oxford) in collaboration with the British Council

- I agree to participate in this research
- I don't agree to participate in this research

End of Block: Welcome message

Start of Block: PART 1: Please answer these personal questions.

PART 1: Please answer these general questions.

In what country is your university based? (Drop Down)

Commented [KS1]: Will be distribute to all 50 countries or just a selected number?

What is the name of your university? (We will not disclose the name of your university in our report, but this helps us to identify public information on your university for our analysis).

-
- I prefer not to disclose this information

What is your position/ job in Higher Education?

- Policy-maker
- Director of institution
- Manager of institution
- Head of International Department
- Administrator
- other, please comment
(*add a comment here*)

Is your university or institution
state-owned
private

What are the main languages of instruction at your university? (put them in order of prevalence if more than one)

- 1.
- 2.
- 3.

Commented [HR2]: Ask what percentage of courses/programmes are offered in English (give broad categories).

Add an open box for them to write about EMI provision.

What proportion of courses at your university are taught through English? (These are courses taught through English. Please do not include language courses)

1. None
 2. Less than 25%
 3. 25-50%
 4. 50-75%
 5. more than 75%
 5. All courses
-

How long has your university been teaching courses through the medium of English?

- Less than 10 years
- 10-20 years
- 21-30 years
- 31-40 years
- More than 40 years

At what level of education is English used as a medium of instruction? (tick all that apply)

- Undergraduate
- Technical diplomas and certificates
- Undergraduate degrees
- Postgraduate degrees (e.g. Masters)
- Postgraduate research degrees (e.g. PhD)
- Other (please specify) _____

In what subjects does your university teach in English?

- Social Sciences
 - Humanities
 - Engineering
 - Mathematics
 - Sciences
 - Medical Sciences
 - Creative or fine arts
 - Other (please specify) _____
-

Please describe the types of programs in English you offer? (tick all that apply)

- Full degrees in English
 - Partial degree courses in English (e.g. only some subjects and modules must be taken in English)
 - Elective content courses in English
 - Other _____
-

Is there an English language proficiency requirement to enter your English medium programmes?

- Yes
 - No
 - Don't Know
 - Only for certain students (please explain)
-

If you are familiar with the requirements, please provide the minimum score required to enter EMI degrees at the university (e.g. TOEIC, TOEFL, IELTS, etc)

- TOEIC _____
- TOEFL _____
- IELTS _____
- CEFR
- Cambridge tests
- Other (please specify) _____
- (high schools English scores)

Does your EMI programme attract international students?

Yes

No

If you answered "Yes", please give details below:

Please write the answers in the box

What percentage of your student population is international students?	
Where do the majority of students come from?	

In your opinion, what is the general proficiency in English of students who take English medium courses at your university?

- Very Advanced (e.g. CEFR C2, TOEIC 785+, IELTS 7.5+, TOEFL 96+/590+)
- Advanced (e.g. CEFR C1, TOEIC 685, IELTS 6.5, TOEFL 79/550)
- Upper Intermediate (e.g. CEFR B2, TOEIC 500, IELTS 5.0, TOEFL 53/477)
- Lower Intermediate (e.g. CEFR B1, TOEIC 350, IELTS 3.5, TOEFL 40/433)
- Basic (e.g. CEFR A1/A2, TOEIC 255, IELTS 2.5, TOEFL 19/347)
- I don't know

End of Block: PART 1: Please answer these personal questions.

Start of Block: PART 2: Please answer these questions about your EMI programme.

PART 2: Please answer these questions about language support that is provided to students on EMI programmes.

Commented [KS3]: Does this overlap with language requirement?

Commented [AM4R3]: I think this is a better phrased question than the other one. It could also be split to ask about undergraduate, and postgraduate separately

My university provides the following support to students on the EMI programme:

	Yes	No	I don't know
Preparatory English language courses before starting university studies (e.g. pre-sessional EAP or foundation year)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Language classes throughout the program	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Self-access study support	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
A writing centre	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other (please specify)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

(optional) Please provide any further details about language support offered.

My university provides the following support for staff:

	Yes	No	I don't know
Mentoring on EMI program	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
In-house training for EMI teachers	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Opportunities to enroll on external courses	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Online training materials	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other (please specify)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

(optional) Please provide further details below about training (e.g. length of course, content of course, etc.)

Page Break

What do you think are the main reasons that students choose to study in English medium degree programs or courses?

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree
To practice or learn English	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Interest in the academic subject or content	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
To experience EMI	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Status of the university	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Job opportunities	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Study abroad opportunities	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Convenient location	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other (please specify)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

What are the objectives for your institution to offer the English medium courses, and how important are these aims for your institution?

	Not important at all	Not important	Important	Very important
To attract foreign students who do not know the local language	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
To create a multicultural environment with international students	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
To prepare local students for the global job market	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
To improve the intercultural competences of local students	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
To improve the profile of the university in your country context	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
To build partnerships with universities abroad, e.g. through joint degree or exchange programs	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
To attract top students to the university	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
To attract international teaching staff	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
To attract foreign students for the future work force of your country	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Commented [HR5]: Need to make these statements more accessible.
Check for use of low frequency words and replace

To provide quality education for students from developing countries

To enroll foreign students in subject areas for which there is a lack of domestic student enrolment

To increase university revenue from international student fees

To what extent do the following factors cause difficulties in running of English medium courses at your university?

	Not a problem at all	Its not really a problem	It is a problem	It is a big problem
Lack of enrolment of international students	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Lack of enrolment of domestic students	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Lack of support from university for lecturers	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Low English proficiency of foreign students	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Insufficient proficiency in English of domestic student	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Low English proficiency of teaching staff	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Low English proficiency of administrative staff	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Low proficiency in the local language of international students	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Mixed language ability of students in the same course	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Differences in academic ability of students in the same course	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

End of Block: Part 5: EMI now and future
